

Testing Mindfulness and Success as Mediators on the Relationship between Socioemotional Competencies and Happiness

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Abstract

This study examined how socioemotional competencies (SECs) relate to happiness, with mindfulness and success as potential mediators. Among 224 participants (69% women; mean age 23.29) from the U.S. and Nepal, SECs were significantly linked to mindfulness ($\beta = .35, p < .001$), success ($\beta = .38, p < .001$), and subjective happiness ($\beta = .39, p < .001$). Mindfulness showed a direct association with subjective happiness ($\beta = .27, p < .001$) but did not mediate the SECs and happiness relationship. Success emerged as a significant mediator ($\beta = .33, p < .001$), indicating its role in translating SECs into happiness. Additionally, U.S. participants reported higher subjective happiness than those from Nepal ($\beta = .15, p < .01$), suggesting cultural influences. These results highlight the complementary roles of SECs, mindfulness, and success in fostering happiness and emphasize the need for culturally sensitive interventions.

Keywords: Socioemotional competencies, social emotional learning, success, mindfulness, happiness, cultural differences

INTRODUCTION

Happiness and success are fundamental components of human well-being. Success, often defined as achieving personal or professional goals, contributes to a sense of fulfillment and supports emotional and psychological health (Diener, 2009; Seligman, 2011). Through enhanced self-efficacy and emotional regulation core aspects of socioemotional competencies (SECs) success can also foster greater resilience and life satisfaction, benefits that are further supported by mindfulness practices (Duckworth et al., 2007; Lyubomirsky, 2008). Subjective happiness, in turn, may not only result from success but also promote it, highlighting a dynamic and reciprocal relationship between these constructs (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005).

Socioemotional competencies (SECs) refer to the set of psychological skills that enable individuals to manage emotions, build relationships, and make responsible decisions across diverse life settings (Durlak et al., 2022; Niemi, 2020). These competencies include self-awareness, self-management, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making (Durlak et al., 2022). Individuals with strong SECs tend to form positive social connections, adapt to challenges, and attain goals that contribute to both success and happiness (Mahoney et al., 2022; Weissberg et al., 2015). Yet, the underlying mechanisms through which SECs influence happiness remain underexplored.

One possible mechanism is mindfulness, defined as the intentional, non-judgmental awareness of the present moment (Kabat-Zinn, 2003). Mindfulness has been shown to enhance several SEC domains, especially self-awareness and emotional regulation (Javadzade et al., 2024). By supporting attentional control, stress reduction, and emotional resilience, mindfulness contributes to greater well-being (Baer, 2018; Tang et al., 2015). Neuroscientific evidence also highlights the role of mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT) in strengthening self-regulation and prosocial behavior (Davidson et al., 2003), reinforcing its potential as a psychological pathway linking SECs and happiness.

While mindfulness is often treated as an outcome of socioemotional development, limited empirical research has investigated its mediating role in the relationship between SEC's

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Received : 17 July 2025

Accepted : 8 October 2025

Online Published : 22 December 2025

2025 JSER, Available online at
<https://www.journalser.com>

Cite this article as: Balayar, B. B., Langlais, M. R., Thapa, S. S. (2025). Testing mindfulness and success as mediators on the relationship between socioemotional competencies and happiness. *Journal of Social and Educational Research*, 4(2), 107-114. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17864057>

and happiness. Similarly, success, though traditionally seen as a result of socioemotional functioning, may also act as a mediator by reinforcing self-belief and emotional satisfaction through goal achievement (Abele et al., 2016; Lyubomirsky, 2008). However, these potential mediating pathways have not been sufficiently tested within an integrated model.

This study aims to address this gap by examining the dual mediating roles of mindfulness and success in the relationship between socioemotional competencies and happiness. Incorporating participants from both the United States and Nepal, the study adds a cross-cultural perspective to better understand how these psychological constructs interact across different contexts.

Diverse perspectives on happiness

Building on the understanding of happiness as a key outcome of socioemotional competencies, it is important to recognize that happiness is a multifaceted construct shaped by psychological, philosophical, and cultural perspectives. Broadly conceptualized as subjective well-being, happiness is influenced by personal experiences, emotional regulation, social support, and a sense of fulfillment (Diener et al., 1999; Stewart & Suldo, 2011). Scholars commonly distinguish between two primary dimensions: hedonic happiness, which emphasizes pleasure and the avoidance of discomfort, and eudaimonic happiness, which centers on meaning, personal growth, and the realization of one's potential (Haybron, 2003; Ryff & Keyes, 1995; Seligman, 2011).

From the eudaimonic perspective, models such as that of Ryff and Keyes (1995) highlight essential dimensions of well-being, including autonomy, purpose, mastery, self-acceptance, and positive relationships. Complementing this psychological framework, Buddhist psychology introduces the notion of authentic-durable happiness, grounded in mindfulness and acceptance of the present moment (Dambrun & Ricard, 2011; Ricard, 2014). This tradition emphasizes liberation from self-centered desires and a shift toward selfless awareness as the foundation for sustained inner peace (Pellerin et al., 2022). These philosophical and psychological approaches converge with empirical research demonstrating that SECs are positively associated with happiness particularly when mindfulness practices enhance emotional awareness and satisfaction in everyday life (Bajaj et al., 2018; Chernyshenko et al., 2018; Ricard, 2014).

Cultural context further shapes how happiness is experienced, understood, and pursued. Cultural values influence emotional expression, self-construal, and the meanings attached to well-being (Ford et al., 2015; Myers & Diener, 1995; Uchida & Oishi, 2016). For example, some cultures associate happiness with personal achievement and self-esteem, while others prioritize social harmony, interdependence, and collective well-being (Uchida & Oishi, 2016). Buddhist traditions, in particular, promote emotional regulation and resilience through mindful acceptance, offering a culturally grounded pathway to durable happiness (Ricard, 2014).

In light of these diverse perspectives, the present study positions happiness not merely as an individual psychological outcome, but as a construct shaped by internal competencies such as SECs and mindfulness as well as broader sociocultural dynamics. This holistic view supports the rationale for exploring how mindfulness and success may jointly mediate the relationship between SECs and happiness across varied cultural contexts.

Mindfulness and success as mediators between socioemotional competencies and happiness

Socioemotional competencies (SECs) encompass essential emotional and interpersonal skills such as empathy, self-regulation, relationship-building, and responsible decision-making (Durlak et al., 2022). According to the CASEL framework, these competencies develop within layered social systems from individual and family environments to schools and broader communities and are crucial for adaptive functioning and well-being (Mahoney et al., 2022). Drawing from cognitive psychology and emotional intelligence models, SECs are known to promote self-awareness, resilience, and positive social engagement, thereby laying the foundation for both success and happiness (Feuerborn & Gueldner, 2019; Stewart & Suldo, 2011; Weissberg et al., 2015).

One key mechanism through which SECs may exert their influence on happiness is mindfulness, the practice of maintaining present-moment awareness with openness and non-judgment (Kabat-Zinn, 1994). Closely aligned with core SEC domains, mindfulness fosters emotional regulation, self-awareness, and attentional control (Baer, 2018; Rosenbaum & Bohart, 2021). Though rooted in ancient Buddhist traditions, mindfulness has been widely adapted into contemporary therapeutic approaches and is recognized for its ability to reduce stress, improve mental clarity, and cultivate self-compassion (Bodhi, 2011; Davidson et al., 2003). Interventions such as Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) and mindfulness-based cognitive therapy (MBCT) have demonstrated significant improvements in emotional balance, resilience, and overall psychological functioning (Guendelman et al., 2017; Kabat-Zinn, 2003). While traditionally treated as an outcome of socioemotional growth, mindfulness is increasingly viewed as a mediating factor that helps explain how SECs lead to enhanced well-being.

A second critical pathway is success, broadly defined as the attainment of meaningful personal or professional goals. Success contributes to well-being by enhancing self-efficacy and providing a sense of fulfillment that is often rooted in strong SECs (Duckworth et al., 2007). Diener (2012) observed that individuals who achieve success whether through income, job satisfaction, or goal completion typically report greater happiness. However, this relationship is complex. As Kahneman and Deaton (2010) point out, while income improves well-being up to a certain threshold, its impact tends to plateau beyond that point. Long-term happiness appears more closely linked to enduring forms of success, such as personal growth and quality relationships, than to material achievements alone (Lyubomirsky et al., 2005).

Emerging literature has begun to conceptualize success not only as an outcome but also as a mediator that translates the benefits of SECs into increased happiness (Abele et al., 2016; Alzahrani et al., 2019). By fostering goal-directed behavior, social adaptability, and emotional perseverance, SECs may empower individuals to succeed across various domains, which in turn enhances life satisfaction. Yet, further research is needed to clarify how different forms of success academic, professional, or relational mediate the relationship between SECs and subjective well-being, particularly across culturally diverse populations (Diener et al., 1999; Uchida & Oishi, 2016). Taken together, mindfulness and success may serve as parallel or complementary pathways through which SECs contribute to happiness. Understanding their mediating roles is essential for designing integrated interventions that cultivate both emotional skills and goal achievement, thereby promoting more holistic and sustainable well-being.

Current research

The present study investigates the relationship between Social and Emotional Competencies (SECs) and happiness by examining the potential mediating roles of mindfulness and perceived success. Specifically, it aims to: (a) analyze the associations among SECs, mindfulness, success, and happiness; and (b) assess whether mindfulness and perceived success mediate the relationship between SECs and happiness.

While previous research has examined these constructs independently such as the effects of mindfulness practices on well-being (e.g., de Carvalho et al., 2017; Guendelman et al., 2017) and the role of SECs in emotional regulation (Mahoney et al., 2022), there is limited empirical work integrating all four variables within a single model. Some studies (e.g., Alahari, 2017; Chernyshenko et al., 2018) suggest that mindfulness and success may serve as potential pathways through which SECs influence happiness. However, a comprehensive understanding of their interrelationships remains underdeveloped.

This study seeks to address that gap by testing an integrated mediation model that examines how mindfulness and perceived success function as mechanisms linking SECs to happiness. In doing so, it contributes to the growing literature on emotional well-being by clarifying how psychological competencies and contextual outcomes jointly shape subjective happiness. The research was conducted in two culturally distinct contexts: among university students in the South-Central United States and in Nepal. By including diverse cultural samples, the study also explores whether cultural orientation moderates the strength or direction of these relationships. Based on the theoretical and empirical background, the following hypotheses were proposed:

H1. SECs will be positively associated with happiness, mindfulness and success.

H2. Mindfulness and success will independently mediate the relationship between SECs and happiness.

H3. Cultural orientation will influence the relationship between SECs and happiness.

H4. Mindfulness and emotion regulation difficulties have a serial mediating role between social media addiction and subjective well-being

METHOD

Procedures and participants

A total of 224 undergraduate students from two universities were recruited through nonprobability convenience sampling (Ary et al., 2018), including 154 participants from the United States and 70 from Nepal. Professors and teaching staff at both universities were asked to distribute an online survey link to students who participated voluntarily. The survey was administered in English and pilot-tested with a small group to ensure clarity. Data were collected between summer 2022 and spring 2023. Nepalese participants were required to be 18 years or older, proficient in English, and familiar with Buddhist culture. U.S. participants were undergraduate students aged 18 or older. All participants provided informed consent online, and institutional review board (IRB) approval was obtained prior to data collection. The U.S. sample was predominantly female (81.2%), with 14.3% identifying as male and a small proportion identifying as non-binary or choosing not to disclose their gender. In terms of race/ethnicity, 38.3% identified as Non-Hispanic White, 24.7% as Latino/Hispanic, 19.5% as Black/African American, and 11.1% as Asian. In contrast, the Nepalese sample was 54.3% male and predominantly Asian (90%). Relationship status varied across groups, with the majority being single in both samples (54.5% in the U.S. and 68.6% in Nepal). The average age was 22.5 years (SD = 5.72) for U.S. participants and 25 years (SD = 6.3) for Nepalese participants.

Measures

Socioemotional Competencies (SEC). SECs were assessed using the 25-item scale by Zhou and Ee (2012), aligned with the CASEL framework (CASEL, 2008). The scale covers five domains: self-awareness, social awareness, self-management, relationship management, and responsible decision-making (5 items each). Sample items include: "I know what I am thinking and doing" (self-awareness) and "I stay calm in stressful situations" (self-management). Items were rated on a 6-point Likert scale (1 = not at all true of me to 6 = always true of me). Internal consistency was strong ($\alpha = .91$; subscales $\alpha = .74-.82$).

Subjective Happiness. Happiness was measured using the 4-item Subjective Happiness Scale (Lyubomirsky & Lepper, 1999). Participants responded using a 7-point Likert scale (1 = less happy, 7 = very happy), with higher scores indicating greater subjective happiness. The scale demonstrated acceptable internal consistency ($\alpha = .76$).

Mindfulness. Mindfulness was captured using the 14-item Freiburg Mindfulness Inventory (FMI). An example item is: "I am open to the experience of the present moment." Responses ranged from 1 (never) to 4 (almost always), with higher total scores indicating greater mindfulness. The scale demonstrated strong internal consistency ($\alpha = .89$).

Table 1. Correlations among the study variables (N = 224)

	N	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	1	2	3	4
1- Happiness	224	4.44	1.02	-.33	.53	-			
2- SECs	224	4.44	.68	-.57	1.03	.41**	-		
3- Mindfulness	224	2.87	.57	-.24	-.17	.41**	.46**	-	
4- Success	224	4.28	.93	-.45	.36	.49**	.52**	.48**	-

** $p < .001$

Success. Perceived life success was assessed using the Life Success Measure Scale (Parker & Chusmir, 1992), which includes items such as “How well was your overall academic achievement?” rated from 1 (not at all good) to 6 (very good). Internal consistency was high ($\alpha = .89$).

Cultural context. Participants country of origin (1 = Nepal, 2 = U.S.) was included as a control variable.

Data analysis process

Missing data were assessed and found to be minimal (4% overall). Little’s MCAR test confirmed the data were missing completely at random, $\chi^2(2465) = 2382.00$, $p = .882$ (Tabachnick et al., 2013). In the U.S. sample, 3% of cases were excluded due to incomplete responses, resulting in 154 usable cases. After data cleaning, both samples were combined for analysis (N = 224).

To address the hypothesis of this study, correlation analysis was used to examine associations between variables, and Mplus v8.0 (Muthén & Muthén, 2006) was employed to estimate a mediation model. Mplus uses estimation procedures to handle missing data using full-information maximum likelihood, which fits the covariance structure directly to the available data for each participant and does not rely on pairwise or listwise deletion (Kline, 2011). The mediation model was conducted using structural equation modeling to test the relations among the primary study variables, which assesses the magnitude and significance of relations among the model’s exogenous (independent) and endogenous (mediator and/or dependent) variables. This approach is advantageous because it can simultaneously test for the direct and indirect (such as mediated) effects, which is not possible with linear regression (Stage et al., 2004). Each of the assumptions associated with structural equation modeling were met, including

homoscedasticity, multivariate normality, and minimal multicollinearity (Kline, 2011).

The SEM approach used was path analysis, which included the direct effect of the independent variable, SECs, to the dependent variable, happiness. Two separate mediation pathways were conducted: one with mindfulness as a mediator and the other with success as the mediator. Mplus captures indirect effects with delta standard errors (Muthén & Muthén, 2006). Additionally, we included age and the source of the data (i.e., U.S. or Nepal) as control variables by regressing on the dependent variable (Kline, 2011). We also included gender as a covariate given the gender imbalance in the study. However, the results did not significantly change the main findings and therefore are not displayed for parsimony.

RESULTS

A Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to examine the relationships among SECs, mindfulness, success, and happiness. As shown in Table 1, all variables were positively and significantly correlated. Happiness demonstrated moderate positive correlations with SECs ($r = .41$, $p < .01$), mindfulness ($r = .41$, $p < .01$), and success ($r = .49$, $p < .01$). SECs showed strong correlations with mindfulness ($r = .46$, $p < .01$) and success ($r = .52$, $p < .01$), while mindfulness was moderately correlated with success ($r = .48$, $p < .01$). These findings indicate robust associations between socioemotional competencies, mindfulness, perceived success, and subjective happiness, supporting the study’s hypotheses.

Results of both path analyses are presented in Figure 1 (the models are combined in this illustration for parsimony).

Table 2. Tests of Mediation for Path Analysis Models (N = 224)

Paths	Mplus estimate of indirect effects			
	Total Effect	Direct Effect	Indirect Effect	95% CI for Indirect Effect
SECs -> mindfulness -> happiness	.39 (.06)***	.39 (.06)***	.00 (.00)	[.00, .00]
SECs -> success -> happiness	.58 (.09)***	.50 (.08)***	.08 (.01)***	[.06, .11]

Note. Mplus estimates of indirect effects reflect standardized coefficients. CI = confidence interval, SECs = socioemotional competencies. *** $p < .001$.

Figure 1. *Path analyses of hypothesized mediation models*. SECs = socioemotional competencies; *** $p < .001$; ** $p < .01$; * $p < .05$

The first model, which tested mindfulness as a mediator, displayed poor model fit $\chi^2(1) = 69.32, p < .001$; comparative fit index (CFI) = .62; RMSEA = .55; standardized root mean square residual (SRMR) = .14). In this model, SECs were significantly associated with both mindfulness ($\beta = .35, p < .001$) and happiness ($\beta = .39, p < .001$). Additionally, mindfulness was significantly associated with happiness ($\beta = .27, p < .001$). The source variable was also significant ($\beta = .15, p < .01$), with individuals from the United States reporting higher levels of happiness compared to individuals from Nepal.

The second model, which tested success as a mediator, displayed adequate model fit $\chi^2(1) = 2.43, p = .12$; CFI = .99; RMSEA = .08; SRMR = .03). In this model, SECs were significantly associated with both success ($\beta = .38, p < .001$) and happiness ($\beta = .39, p < .001$). Additionally, success was significantly associated with happiness ($\beta = .33, p < .001$). These results provide partial support for hypotheses 2. Source was also significant in both models ($\beta = .15, p < .01$), with individuals from the United States reporting higher levels of happiness compared to those residing in Nepal, supporting Hypothesis 3.

Results of the indirect pathways are presented in Table 2. Success appears to significantly mediate the relationship between SECs and happiness, although the direct pathway between SECs and happiness remains significant. However, mindfulness did not mediate the relationship between SECs and happiness, although both SECs and mindfulness were directly associated with happiness.

DISCUSSION

This study provides valuable insights into the interrelationships among socioemotional competencies (SECs), mindfulness, success, and happiness. Correlational analysis revealed strong, significant associations among these variables, supporting previous theoretical and empirical claims about their role in psychological well-being (Abele et al., 2016; Chernyshenko et al., 2018). Specifically, happiness was moderately associated

with SECs, mindfulness, and success, while SECs demonstrated strong links with both mindfulness and success underscoring their foundational role in shaping internal experiences and external outcomes.

Path analyses revealed more nuanced dynamics. The model testing mindfulness as a mediator showed poor fit, although direct paths from SECs to both mindfulness and happiness were significant. Mindfulness also directly predicted happiness, confirming its value as an independent contributor to well-being (Guendelman et al., 2017; Kirmayer, 2015; Ludwig & Kabat-Zinn, 2008). However, it did not mediate the SECs and happiness relationship, suggesting that while mindfulness supports happiness, it is not the mechanism through which SECs exert their influence. This aligns with previous research indicating that SECs and mindfulness may operate through distinct psychological pathways (Baer, 2018; Feuerborn & Gueldner, 2019; Filipe et al., 2021; Tang et al., 2015).

In contrast, success emerged as a significant mediator. Individuals with higher SECs reported greater perceived success, which, in turn, was associated with increased happiness demonstrating a cascading effect (Alzahrani et al., 2019). These findings suggest that SECs influence happiness both directly and indirectly by fostering goal achievement. This combined influence reinforces prior evidence on their contribution to emotional regulation, social functioning, and life satisfaction (Niemi, 2020; Mahoney et al., 2022).

Although mindfulness did not serve a mediating role, its strong direct associations with both SECs and happiness highlight its continued relevance. As an emotional stabilizer, mindfulness may enhance the effectiveness of SECs by complementing goal-directed behavior with present-moment awareness and internal balance (Baer, 2018; Tang et al., 2015).

Cultural differences also emerged: U.S. participants reported significantly higher happiness levels than those from Nepal. Although cultural factors were not directly analyzed, this finding suggests that societal norms and values may influence

how individuals experience happiness and engage with constructs like SECs, mindfulness, and success (Ford et al., 2015; Uchida & Oishi, 2016).

Taken together, these findings illustrate an interconnected psychological framework. SECs form the foundation for both success and well-being, while mindfulness contributes directly to emotional resilience. Success, in turn, transforms social-emotional strengths into tangible life outcomes. Rather than functioning in isolation, these constructs interact to support purposeful living, emotional balance, and regulation. While SECs relate more to the goal oriented and subjective aspects of happiness, mindfulness may foster a more enduring, grounded form of well-being (Ricard, 2014).

Implications

This study highlights the central role of SECs in promoting happiness through both direct and indirect pathways. Theoretically, the findings emphasize the dual role of SECs supporting both emotional regulation and achievement-oriented behavior, together contribute to subjective well-being. Moreover, the distinct contributions of mindfulness and success point to the importance of exploring both hedonic (pleasure-based) and eudaimonic (meaning-based) components of happiness.

Practically, the results support the development of integrated interventions that combine socioemotional and mindfulness training. Programs such as mindfulness-based emotional intelligence development may promote both immediate and long-term well-being (Feuerborn & Gueldner, 2019). While mindfulness did not mediate the SEC and happiness relationship, its direct effect on happiness affirms its value as a resilience enhancing tool. Meanwhile, the mediating role of success underscores the importance of supporting goal setting and achievement skills within SEC-focused interventions.

Culturally, differences between U.S. and Nepalese participants highlight the need for culturally responsive approaches. Cultural values likely shape how constructs such as success, mindfulness, and happiness are experienced and expressed. These findings point to the importance of adapting social emotional learning (SEL) programs to align with cultural norms and contextual realities, ensuring inclusivity and relevance across populations.

Limitations, conclusion, and future directions

This study offers important insights into how socioemotional competencies (SECs), mindfulness, and success contribute to happiness. SECs were found to influence happiness both directly and indirectly through success, while mindfulness emerged as a direct but non-mediating factor. Regardless, several limitations should be acknowledged. The use of self-reported, cross-sectional data limits causal inferences and may introduce bias. Additionally, the sample was predominantly women; although gender was not significant in this study, future studies are encouraged to recruit larger samples using

stratified random sampling according to gender to verify these findings. Key contextual variables such as socioeconomic status, and field of study were not analyzed, and the cultural scope was limited to two countries. Future studies are encouraged to examine these potential confounding variables.

Future research should use longitudinal and experimental designs to explore causality and include a wider range of variables such as resilience, personality, or compassion. Expanding to more diverse cultural contexts and incorporating mixed methods will strengthen the evidence base. Studies in applied settings can also help develop integrated interventions that combine SECs and mindfulness to promote both personal success and emotional well-being.

In sum, this study highlights the complementary roles of SECs, mindfulness, and success in fostering happiness and underscores the need for holistic, culturally informed approaches to psychological growth and well-being.

Ethical approval: This study was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines of the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Institutional Review Board of University of North Texas (Approval No. IRB# 22-58).

Consent to participate: All data were collected online with informed consent obtained from participants. The Institutional Review Board (IRB) approved the study and waived the requirement for signed documentation due to the online survey format.

Availability of data: The datasets analyzed in this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Competing interests: The authors declare no potential conflicts of interest concerning the study, authorship and/or publication of this study.

Funding: The authors received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

REFERENCES

- Abele, A. E., Hagmaier, T., & Spurk, D. (2016). Does career success make you happy? The mediating role of multiple subjective success evaluations. *Journal of Happiness Studies: An Interdisciplinary Forum on Subjective Well-Being*, *17*(4), 1615–1633. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-015-9662-4>
- Alahari, U. (2017). Supporting socio-emotional competence and psychological well-being of school psychologists through mindfulness practice. *Contemporary School Psychology*, *21*(4), 369–379. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40688-017-0154-x>
- Alzahrani, M., Alharbi, M., & Alodwani, A. (2019). The effect of social-emotional competence on children academic achievement and behavioral development. *International Education Studies*, *12*(12), 141–149. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ies.v12n12p141>
- Ary, D., Jacobs, L. C., Irvine, C. K. S., & Walker, D. (2018).

- Introduction to research in education* (10th ed.). Cengage Learning.
- Baer, R. (2018). Mindfulness practice. In S. C. Hayes & S. G. Hofmann (Eds.), *Process-based CBT: The science and core clinical competencies of cognitive behavioral therapy* (pp. 389–402). New Harbinger Publications, Inc.
- Bajaj, B., Gupta, R., & Sengupta, S. (2018). Emotional stability and self-esteem as mediators between mindfulness and happiness. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 20(7), 2211–2226. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-018-0046-4>
- Bodhi, B. (2011). What does mindfulness really mean? A canonical perspective. *Contemporary Buddhism*, 12, 19–39. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14639947.2011.564813>
- CASEL. (2020). *What is SEL?* Retrieved from <https://casel.org/what-is-sel>
- CASEL. (2008). Assessment, tools. Retrieved from <https://casel.org/state-resource-center/assessment-tools/>
- Chernyshenko, O. S., Kankaraš, M., & Drasgow, F. (2018). *Social and emotional skills for student success and well-being: Conceptual framework for the OECD study on social and emotional skills* (OECD Education Working Papers No. 173). OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/db1d8e59-en>
- Davidson, R. J., Kabat-Zinn, J., Schumacher, J., Rosenkranz, M., Müller, D., Santorelli, S. F., Urbanowski, F., Harrington, A., Bonus, K., & Sheridan, J. F. (2003). Alterations in brain and immune function produced by mindfulness meditation. *Psychosomatic Medicine*, 65(4), 564–570. <https://doi.org/10.1097/01.PSY.0000077505.67574.E3>
- Dambrun, M., & Ricard, M. (2011). Self-centeredness and selflessness: A theory of self-based psychological functioning and its consequences for happiness. *Review of General Psychology*, 15(2), 138–157. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0023059>
- de Carvalho, J. S., Pinto, A. M., & Marôco, J. (2017). Results of a mindfulness-based social-emotional learning program on Portuguese elementary students and teachers: A quasi-experimental study. *Mindfulness*, 8(2), 337–350. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-016-0603-z>
- Diener, E., Suh, E. M., Lucas, R. E., & Smith, H. L. (1999). Subjective well-being: Three decades of progress. *Psychological Bulletin*, 125(2), 276–302. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.125.2.276>
- Diener, E. (Ed.). (2009). *The science of well-being: The collected works of Ed Diener* (Social Indicators Research Series, Vol. 37). Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-2350-6>
- Duckworth, A. L., Peterson, C., Matthews, M. D., & Kelly, D. (2007). Grit: Perseverance and passion for long-term goals. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 92(6), 1087–1101. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.92.6.1087>
- Durlak, J. A., Mahoney, J. L., & Boyle, A. E. (2022). What we know, and what we need to find out about universal, school-based social and emotional learning programs for children and adolescents: A review of meta-analyses and directions for future research. *Psychological Bulletin*, 148(11-12), 765–782. <https://doi.org/10.1037/bul0000383>
- Feuerborn, L. L., & Gueldner, B. (2019). Mindfulness and social-emotional competencies: Proposing connections through a review of the research. *Mindfulness*, 10, 1707–1720. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-019-01101-1>
- Filipe, M. G., Magalhães, S., Veloso, A. S., Costa, A. F., Ribeiro, L., Araújo, P., Limpo, T. (2021). Exploring the effects of meditation techniques used by mindfulness-based programs on the cognitive, social-emotional, and academic skills of children: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 660650. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.660650>
- Ford, B. Q., Dmitrieva, J. O., Heller, D., Chentsova-Dutton, Y., Grossmann, I., Tamir, M., Uchida, Y., Koopmann-Holm, B., Floerke, V. A., Uhrig, M., Bokhan, T., & Mauss, I. B. (2015). Culture shapes whether the pursuit of happiness predicts higher or lower well-being. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: General*, 144(6), 1053–1062. <https://doi.org/10.1037/xge0000108>
- Guendelman, S., Medeiros, S., & Rampes, H. (2017). Mindfulness and emotion regulation: Insights from neurobiological, psychological, and clinical studies. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, 208068. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00220>
- Haybron, D. M. (2003). What do we want from a theory of happiness? *Metaphilosophy*, 34(3), 305–329. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9973.00275>
- Javadzade, N., Esmaeili, S.V., Omranifard, V. et al. Effect of mindfulness-based stress reduction (MBSR) program on depression, emotion regulation, and sleep problems: A randomized controlled trial study on depressed elderly. *BMC Public Health*, 24(1), 271. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-024-17759-9>
- Kabat-Zinn, J. (1994). *Mindfulness meditation for everyday life*. Piatkus.
- Kabat-Zinn, J. (2003). *Wherever you go, there you are: Mindfulness meditation in everyday life*. Hyperion.
- Kahneman, D., & Deaton, A. (2010). High income improves evaluation of life but not emotional well-being. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 107(38), 16489–16493. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1011492107>
- Kirmayer, L. J. (2015). Mindfulness in cultural context. *Transcultural Psychiatry*, 52(4), 447–469. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1363461515598949>
- Kline, R. B. (2011). *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling* (3rd ed.). Guilford Press.
- Ludwig, D. S., & Kabat-Zinn, J. (2008). Mindfulness in medicine. *JAMA*, 300(11), 1350–1352. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jama.300.11.1350>
- Lyubomirsky, S., King, L., & Diener, E. (2005). The benefits of frequent positive affect: Does happiness lead to success? *Psychological Bulletin*, 131(6), 803–855. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.131.6.803>
- Lyubomirsky, S., & Lepper, H. (1999). A measure of subjective happiness: Preliminary reliability and construct validation. *Social Indicators Research*, 46 (2), 137–155. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1006824100041>
- Lyubomirsky, S. (2008). *The how of happiness: A new approach to getting the life you want*. penguin.
- Muthén, L. K., & Muthén, B. O. (2006). *Mplus: Statistical Analysis with Latent Variables; User's Guide; [Version 4.1]*. Muthén.
- Niemi, K. (2020, December 15). CASEL is updating the most widely recognized definition of social-emotional learning: Here's why. *The 74 Million*. Retrieved from <https://www.the74million.org/article/niemi-casel-is->

- updating-the-most-widely-recognized-definition-of-social-emotional-learning-heres-why/
 Parker, B., & Chusmir, L. H. (1992). Development and validation of a life-success measures scale. *Psychological Reports*, 70(2), 627–637. <https://doi.org/10.2466/PR0.70.2.627-637>
- Pellerin, N., Dambrun, M., & Raufaste, E. (2022). Selflessness meets higher and more stable happiness: An experience sampling study of the joint dynamics of selflessness and happiness. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 23(6), 3127–3142. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-022-00503-8>
- Ricard, M. (2014). A Buddhist view of happiness. *Journal of Law and Religion*, 29(1), 14–29. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24739083>
- Rosenbaum, R., & Bohart, A. (2021). Mindfulness is full engagement. *The Humanistic Psychologist*, 49(1), 122–132. <https://doi.org/10.1037/hum0000166>
- Ryff, C. D., & Keyes, C. L. (1995). The structure of psychological well-being revisited. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 69(4), 719–727. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.69.4.719>
- Seligman, M. E. (2011). *Flourish: A visionary new understanding of happiness and well-being*. New York, NY: Free press.
- Stage, F. K., Carter, H. C., & Nora, A. (2004). Path Analysis: An Introduction and Analysis of a Decade of Research. *The Journal of Educational Research*, 98(1), 5–13. <https://doi.org/10.3200/JOER.98.1.5-13>
- Stewart, T., & Suldo, S. (2011). Relationships between social support sources and early adolescents' mental health: The moderating effect of student achievement level. *Psychology in the Schools*, 48(10), 1016–1033. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pits.20607>
- Tabachnick, B. G., Fidell, L. S., & Ullman, J. B. (2013). Using multivariate statistics (Vol. 5, No. 7). Boston, MA: Pearson.
- Tang, Y., Hölzel, B. K., and Posner, M. I. (2015). The neuroscience of mindfulness meditation. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 16(4), 213–225. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn3916>
- Uchida, Y., & Oishi, S. (2016). The happiness of individuals and the collective. *Japanese Psychological Research*, 58(1), 125–141. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jpr.12103>
- Weissberg, R. P., Durlak, J. A., Domitrovich, C. E., & Gullotta, T. P. (2015). Social and emotional learning: Past, present, and future. In R. P. Weissberg, J. A. Durlak, C. E. Domitrovich, & T. P. Gullotta (Eds.), *Handbook of social and emotional learning: Research and practice* (pp. 3–19). The Guilford Press
- Zhou, M. & Ee J. (2012). Development and validation of the social emotional competence questionnaire (SECQ). *The International Journal of Emotional Education*, 4(2), 27–42. <https://doi.org/10.1037/t69172-000>
- Young, K. S., & Rodgers, R. C. (1998). The relationship between depression and internet addiction. *Cyberpsychology & Behavior*, 1(1), 25–28.
- Yu, J. J., Kim, H., & Hay, I. (2013). Understanding Adolescents Problematic Internet Use from a Social/Cognitive and Addiction Research Framework. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(6), 2682–2689. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2013.06.045>
- Yüksekbilgili, N. Ş. (2020). Bilinçli farkındalık düzeyi ile bireysel mutluluk düzeyi arasındaki ilişki üzerine bir araştırma. *Uluslararası Akademik Yönetim Bilimleri Dergisi*, 6(8), 63–72

How to Cite this Article

Balayar, Y. B., Langlais, M. R., Thapa, S. S. (2025). Testing mindfulness and success as mediators on the relationship between socioemotional competencies and happiness. *Journal of Social and Educational Research*, 4(2), 107–114. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17864057>

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